

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

REVIEW ARTICLE OF BHRINGRAJ**Nagambika. M***, Mavya Sri. A, Sasikumari. P, Kavitha. K, Saicharan D.V, Sai Kishore. V
Bapatla College of Pharmacy, Bapatla – 522101, India.**Abstract:**

Bhringraj [Eclipta prostrate or ecliptaalba] is a famous herb known as benefits in usage of hair growth and disorders of liver. It is a well know in Ayurveda for its medicinal uses, plants extracts of bhringraj have been variety of curves, commonly know as properties of Antihepatotoxicity, Antidiabetic, Antiinflammatoryect. It is an effective medicine for skin diseases related to part of head. And it also improves hair growth, prevents hair growth, prevents hairfall, and treats premature graying of hair. It is more used in chronic skin diseases including prurites, chronic wounds, skin ulcers, ect. And it increses the production of liver form bile. Eclipta alba can found in growing wild in fallow lands of Bangladesh and it is considered as a weed of farmers. The plant consists of several phytoconstituents like oleano0lic acid, ursolic acid ect.And it also reduces constipation

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Please cite this article in press Nagambika.M et al., *Review Article Of Bhringraj*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (12).

INTRODUCTION:

Nature is the major source of various medicine for thousands of years. Among all plants, medicinal plants have greater significance. Medicinal plants are the plants which possess one or more than one medically important substance which are produced by different parts of plants used for the synthesis of new drugs. One of such medicinal plants is bhringraj

which has numerous therapeutic properties like an astringent, depurative, emetic, purgative, nervine tonic, catarrhal, febrifuge, ophthalmic, styptic, tonic, anti-nociceptive, anti-leprotic, anti-hemorrhagic, anti-myotoxic, anti-hyperlipidemic, anti-diabetic, hepatoprotective, diuretic, hypotensive, nootropic, anti-venom, ovicidal and spasmogenic. Bhringraj is a commonly known as false daisy in English.

DESCRIPTION:

Bhringraj, also known as *Eclipta alba*, is an Ayurvedic herb that is a member of the sunflower family:

Bhringraj is a creeping herb with white flowers that resemble daisies. It has long stalks, lance-shaped leaves and grey roots. Bhringraj can grow up to 3 meters tall. It has a long stalk and white-colored flowers which are solitary, winged and about 6 to 8 mm in diameter. The leaves are sessile, lance-shaped and arranged in the opposite orientation. It has distinct cylindrical and grey coloured roots.

Bhringraj is native to India and Southwest America, but it grows in moist places around the world.

Bhringraj may interact with certain medications, including blood pressure and cholesterol medications.

TAXONOMY

KINGDOM	PLANTAE
Subkingdom	Viridaplantae
Infrakingdom	Streptophyta
Division	Tracheophyta
Subdivision	Spermatophytina
Infradivision	Angiospermae
Class	Magnoliopsida
Superorder	Asteraanae
Order	Asterales
Family	Asteraceae
Genus	Eclipta L.
Species	Eclipta alba (L.) Hassk.
Common name	False lily, Bhringraj

COMMON NAME

ENGLISH	FALSE DAISY
Sanskrit	Bhrungaraj, Kesharaj, Markava, KesharanjanaKeshara
Hindi	Bhangara, Bhangarayya
Punjabi	Bhangara, Dodhak, Babri
Marathi	Maka
Gujarat	Bhangaro
Bengali	Kesuriya, kesuti
Tamil	Kaikeshi
Telugu	Galagara, Gunta, Galijaeru
Malyalam	Cajenneam, Kanni
Konkani	Mako, Kajalamavu
Asamese	Kehraj
Arabic	Kadim-ul-bint, Radim-el-bint

PHYTOCHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS IN ECLIPTA ALBA

TABLE 1.

1.	Root	Thiophenes, eclipta, hentriacintanol, Eclabatin, Stigmasterol
2.	Stems	Wedelactone
3.	Leaves	Stigmasterol, β -terthienylmethanol, Wedelolactone[1.6%]
4.	Twigs of the plant	Sterols, Ecliptalbine
5.	Seeds	Alkaloids
6.	Aerial part	Amyrin, Luteolin-7-o-glucoside
7.	Bhringraj being a potent hair vitalizer has a host of bioactive constituents including flavonoids.	

TABLE 2.

The plants contain a number of bioactive chemical which there as follows :

Nature of Phyto constituents	Phytoconstituents
Coumestan	Wedelolactone, demethylwedelolactone, demethylwedelolactone-7-glucoside
	Eclalbasaponins VII-X (taraxastanetri-terpene glycosides), eclalbasaponins I-VI (oleananetri-terpene glycosides), eclalbasaponins I-VI (triterpene glycosides), ecliptasaponins Cand D (triterpenoid glycosides), α -amyrin, oleanolic acid, ursolic acid (triterpenoids)
Sterol	Stigmasterol, daucosterol, stigmasterol-3-O-glucoside
Alkaloids	[(20S)(25S)-22,26-imino-cholesta-5,22(N)-dine-3 β -ol] (verazine), [20-epi-3-dehydroxy-3-oxo-5,6-dihydro-4,5-dehydroverazine], [(20R)-4 β -hydroxyverazine], [4 β -hydroxyverazine], [(20R)-25 β -hydroxyverazine], [25 β -hydroxyverazine]
Flavonoids	Luteolin-7-glucoside, luteolin, apigenin, orobol, (isoluteolin)
Sesquiterpene lactones	5-hydroxymethyl-(2, 2':5', 2'')-terthienyltiglate, 5-hydroxymethyl-(2,2':5', 2'')-terthienyl acetate
Terthienyl aldehyde	Ecliptal
Fatty alcohols	Hentriacontanol, heptacosanol
Volatile oils	Heptadecane, 6, 10, 14-trimethyl-2-pentadecanone, <i>n</i> -hexadecanoic acid, pentadecane, eudesma-4(14), 11-diene, phytol, octadic-9-enoic acid, 1,2-benzedi-carboxylic acid diisooctyl ester, (Z,Z)-9, 12-octadecadienoic acid, (Z)-7,11-dimethyl-3-methylene-1, 6,10-dodecatriene, (Z,Z,Z)-1, 5, 9, 9-tetramethyl-1, 4, 7-cycloundecatriene
Saponins	Eclalbatin (triterpenesaponin), dasyscyphin C
Polyacetylinic compounds	α -Terthienylmethanol, polyacetylenes, polyacetylene substituted thiophenes
Phenolic acids	Protocatechuic acid, 4-hydroxy benzoic acid

Eclipata alba (E. alba) possesses numerous pharmacological properties, as outlined below :

ANTI BACTERIAL ACTIVITY :

The water extract of E. alba demonstrates potent activity against bacterial strains like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Bacillus cereus*. However, when diluted beyond 1mg/ml, its efficacy in inhibiting bacteria such as *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and *Klebsiella pneumonia* decreases. The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) results mirrored those of the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), but the MBC was confirmed based on the absence of bacterial growth on culture plates. This suggests the potential for developing potent antibacterial agents from E. alba to counter bacterial infections.

ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY :-

The active compound, 25- betahydroxyverazine, isolated from E.alba, has shown effective antifungal

properties, particularly against *Candida albicans*. Furthermore, E.alba extracts (in vitro) inhibited the growth of *Rhodotorula glutinosa*, *Candida tropicalis*, and *Candida albicans*.

ANTIHELMINTIC ACTIVITY :-

The methanol extract of E.alba was tested for its ability to combat the parasitic worm *Pheretimaphostuman* at doses of 25, 50, 75, and 100 mg/ml. The extract caused worm mortality at 75mg/ml and 100mg/ml, while paralysis was observed at various concentrations.

ANTIMALARIAL ACTIVITY :-

E.alba leaf extract demonstrated antimalarial effects against *Plasmodium berghei* ANKA strains in mice.

HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY :-

E.alba exhibited significant liver- protective effects, countering damage caused by carbon tetrachloride (CCL4), which inhibits liver microsomal drug-metabolizing enzymes. E.alba restored the activity of enzymes such as alkaline phosphatase and lysosomal acid phosphatase, highlighting its ability to protect liver function.

NEUROPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY :-on anxiety, sedation, memory enhancement, antistress, and muscle relaxation at doses of 150 and 300mg/kg body weight. The results showed that the aqueous extract at 300mg/kg and its hydrolyzed fraction at 30mg/kg exhibited nootropic activity. E-alba extracts also reduced aggression in animal models.

IMMUNOMODULATORY ACTIVITY :-

The methanol extract of E.alba was evaluated for its immunomodulatory properties. Compounds like demethylwedelolactone and wedelolactone were found to inhibit trypsin and displayed immunomodulatory potential with IC50 values of 2.9 and 3.0µg/ml.

ANALGESICACTIVITY: -

E.alba extracts and its alkaloid fraction were tested for pain-relieving effects in albino mice using various models. The results indicated that both the ethanol extract and the total alkaloid fraction of E. alba exhibited strong analgesic properties.

DIURETIC ACTIVITY :-

E. alba leaf extract and its alcohol extract were tested in mice for their ability to promote diuresis. The study showed an increase in the excretion of potassium, sodium, and chloride ions after treatment with E. alba extracts.

HYPOLIPIDEMIC ACTIVITY :-

The alcoholic extract of E. alba was investigated for its cholesterol-lowering effects in rats. The extract effectively reduced total cholesterol, serum triglycerides, and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) levels in the treated groups compared to controls.

ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY :-

E. alba methanol extract demonstrated anti-inflammatory effects in Wistar albino rats with carrageenan-induced hind limb edema at doses of 100 and 200mg/kg body weight.

ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVVITY :-

In a study with alloxan-induced diabetic rats, E. alba leaf suspension (2 and 4g/kg body weight) significantly reduced blood glucose and glycosylated

hemoglobin levels while improving hepatic enzyme activities. E.alba is also a key component in a polyherbal formulation known for its diuretic and antidiabetic properties, aiding in pancreatic β-cell regeneration and function.

ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY:-

E. alba extract has potent antioxidant activity, as measured by several assays, including radical scavenging (DPPH) and ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP). The antioxidant effect increases with higher doses of the extract.

ANTICANCER ACTIVITY :-

E.alba extract showed anticancer activity in mice with Ehrlich-Lette ascites carcinoma. The methanol extract improved survival rates and restored hematological parameters. E. alba's coumestans, such as dasyscyphin-(saponin), also showed cytotoxic activity cancer cells and recognized for their potential in preventing prostate and breast cancers.

HAIR GROWTH PROMOTION :-

Petroleum ether and ethanolic extracts of E. alba promoted hair growth in albino rats when applied topically. The number of hair follicles in the anagen phase increased significantly compared to the control group.

MEMORY ENHANCEMENT ; Compounds like β-amyryn, phytosterol, and flavones (including luteolin) in E. alba have shown memory-enhancing properties. Luteolin, in particular, helps minimize cognitive deficits linked to cholinergic dysfunction, as demonstrated in labyrinth tests.

ANTIVENOM ACTIVITY:-

E. alba extracts have antivenom properties, inhibiting phospholipase A2 toxin activity from *Crotalus durissus terrificus* snake venom. Compounds like wedelolactone and coumestans contribute to this activity.

Bhringraj (Ecliptaprostrata) is a traditional herb used in Ayurveda, particularly for hair health. It is known for its multiple health benefits, especially for hair, skin, and general wellness.

1.PROMOTES HAIR GROWTH :-

Bhringraj is widely known for stimulating hair growth. It strengthens hair follicles, reduces hair fall, and helps in preventing baldness. The herb nourishes the scalp, making hair healthier and shinier.

2. PREVENTS PREMATURE GRAYING :-

Regular use of bhringraj helps in delaying premature graying of hair due to its rich nutrient content, which supports melanin production.

3.TREATS DANDRUFF AND SCALP CONDITIONS :-

Bhringraj has antifungal and antibacterial properties, which help treat dandruff, itchy scalp and other scalp infections. It also soothes and nourishes the scalp, keeping it clean and healthy.

4. IMPROVE LIVER FUNTION :-

In Ayurveda, Bhringraj is known as a liver tonic (hepatoprotective). It helps detoxify the liver, promoting better digestion and metabolism, which in turn benefits overall health.

5. BOOSTS SKIN HEALTH :-

Bhringraj oil or extracts are often used in skincare to treat issues like acne, inflammation, and minor skin infections. Its anti-inflammatory properties make it effective in soothing skin irritations.

6. SUPPORTS RESPIRATORY HEALTH :-

The herb has been traditionally used to manage respiratory conditions such as bronchitis and asthma by clearing mucus and easing congestion.

7.Anti-Inflammatory and Antioxidant Properties :-

Bhringraj contains powerful antioxidants and anti-inflammatory compounds that help combat oxidative stress and inflammation, promoting overall health and well-being.

8. PROMOTES BETTER SLEEP :-

Bhringraj is also known for its calming properties, making it beneficial for promoting better sleep and reducing anxiety.

9.SUPPORTS HEALTHY BLOOD CIRCULATION: -

Regular consumption of Bhringraj can improve blood circulation, particularly in the scalp and skin, which supports hair growth and overall skin health.

Bhringraj is available in various forms such as powder, oil, or capsules, and it is typically applied topically or taken as a supplement depending on the intended use.

Eclipta alba, also known as False Daisy or Bhringraj, is a potent herb used in traditional Ayurvedic medicine. It offers many health benefits due to its healing properties. Here are the key benefits :

1. STIMULATES HAIR GROWTH :

Eclipta alba, helps promote hair growth, reduce hair loss, premature graying. It strengthens the scalp and hair follicles.

2. LIVER HEALTH :-

It protects and detoxifies the liver, aiding in the treatment of liver conditions like hepatitis and jaundice.

3.ANTI-INFLAMMATORY AND ANTIOXIDANT :-

Rich in antioxidants, it reduces inflammation and oxidative stress, benefiting conditions like arthritis.

4.IMPROVES SKIN HEALTH :-

Its antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties help treat skin issues like acne, eczema, and promote wound healing.

5. SUPPORTS RESPIRATORY HEALTH :-

Traditionally used for respiratory ailments, it helps relieve conditions like asthma and bronchitis by clearing congestion.

6. AIDS DIGESTION :-

Ecliptaalba supports digestion, reducing bloating and stimulating appetite through enzyme production.

7.FIGHTS INFECTION :-

With antimicrobial properties, it combats infections and strengthens immunity, treating bacterial and fungal conditions.

8. HEART HEALTH :-

It lowers blood pressure and cholesterol, supporting cardiovascular health by protecting against inflammation

9. BOOSTS BRAIN FUNTION :-

Known for its neuroprotective effects, Ecliptaalba enhances memory and cognitive function.

10. KIDNEY SUPPORT :-

Its diuretic effect aids in detoxifying the kidneys and preventing kidney-related issues.Avaliable as oils, powders, or capsules, Ecliptaalba can be applied externally or consumed for overall health benefits.

CONCLUSION:

E. alba is a medicinal plant with a variety of therapeutic properties, including antibacterial, hepatoprotective, neuroprotective, immunomodulatory, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antivenom activities. Additionally, it is widely used for hair growth promotion and dyeing .Its active compounds, including glycosides, triterpenoids, alkaloids, flavonoids, and coumestans, support its wide range of pharmacological activities.

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